

GIS Isn't Working: the use, influence and role of GIS in an applied transport context

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Summary

As transport planning support systems (TPSS) such as models, frameworks and dashboards become widespread in the new tier of sub-national governance in England, it is essential to understand how these systems are being applied, and the ecosystem around them. How far do TPSS, and the abductions they make about society as it really is, follow through into transport policy? What technical and political barriers are there to getting these GIS tools into practice? We use interviews with practitioners across England's sub-national transport bodies (STBs) to understand contemporary attitudes surrounding TPSS and their use cases.

KEYWORDS: Implications of Distributed GIS&T, Spatial Decision Support, GIS&T in State and Regional Government, Geocomputation Methods and Models, GIS and Critical Ethics

1 Introduction

This abstract reckons with the efficacy of some of the most consequential applied GIS systems in England: transport models (Boyce and Williams, 2015). Entire conferences revolve around the nature of such models and innovations in the modelling space (Jin, 2024). Government departments mull over the best use cases and appraisal scenarios for different models and tools, updating them on a regular basis (DfT, 2022). However, in the contemporary context, there is surprisingly little research on how these transport planning support systems (TPSS) have been applied - how tools relate to policy, and how politics relate to tools. In the broadest sense, our co-funded PhD project responds to this by investigating the technical and political infrastructures surrounding TPSS to discuss how they might be employed on a regional basis to help achieve net zero objectives. The part of that project we focus on here zooms in on those political infrastructures, aiming to answer one core question: beyond what TPSS are built to achieve, how are they *understood* within institutional structures, and how does that affect their use and influence?

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The framing of use, influence and role here is drawn from Gudmundsson and Sørensen (2013): ‘use’ is understood in terms of the way models are deployed; their handling and inclusion, ‘role’ is understood as the way that use informs practice, while ‘influence’ is understood in terms of the ultimate policy impact, the contribution to an outcome (p. 39). The point here is to establish a distinction between which TPSS are *present* in an institutional context and the *effect* they have on decision-making. This is fundamentally shaped by if their role is more ‘instrumental’ (affecting a decision that has not yet been made, by providing data) or more ‘symbolic’ (justifying decisions that have already been taken, by providing an *appeal* to data). Hence, as much as we do examine which tools are used, we wish to pose further questions regarding whether such tools *influence* policy and their *role* within that.

2 Background

In 1975, Pack (1975) conducted a survey of US planning departments concerning their use of models across planning. It found that model development was a ‘cottage industry’ of sorts: roughly two thirds of models were built inside the departments where they were used, with external partners contributing the remainder. The practitioners Pack surveyed felt their models were very useful in both projection and project evaluation (1975, p. 196). However, a 2010 study by Göçmen and Ventura in Minnesota found that the situation had completely reversed: planning practitioners lacked awareness of the potential for using models in their work, owing to issues around model complexity, requisite skills, and justifying the use case (p. 177).

In England, similar reductions in public sector knowledge capacity and training might suggest a comparable shift in understanding and use of (T)PSS (Batty, 1994, p. 10). The age of commonplace multimodal studies has passed (Boyce and Williams, 2015, p. 405); within local councils’ planning departments, the number of staff who *practice* planning is less clear. Administrators and managers are more commonplace, with modelling and data analysis often outsourced to consultancies, creating situations where modelling is either unresponsive to the needs of the planning process or brought in too late to respond effectively (te Brömmelstroet, 2010, p. 32). Nationally, the Department for Transport (DfT) provides an increasingly lengthy catalogue of guidance, and academics sit on top, informing what the ‘cutting edge’ of TPSS looks like. However, as Marsden and Reardon (2017) note, two thirds of academic papers in transport studies fail to engage with a tangible, practical use case. As for guidance, DfT advice has historically focused on a more traditional type of modelling, the four-step model (McNally, 2007), somewhat limiting implementation of alternatives.

This evolving situation is the background to our qualitative analysis of the TPSS used by England’s sub-national transport bodies (STBs). STBs were established by the Cities and Local Government Devolution Act 2016, each overseeing a group of local (and combined) authorities (Clark and Williams, 2016). Their core strategic objective is promoting regional economic growth, but they also aim to consider the social and environmental impacts likewise attached to transport (Clark and Williams, 2016, p. 31). STBs can conduct their own business case development, but they also support cases made by their constituent authorities that align with STBs’ objectives; in this respect, TPSS is core to their analytical activities.

3 Methods

This abstract examines 12 interviews conducted with STB staff during 2024; for the wider project, interviews were also undertaken with DfT staff and consultants. Within the STB group, we chose to interview staff who worked closest to the ‘coal face’ of TPSS within their organisation, with common job titles including ‘Technical Lead’ or ‘Head of Modelling’. Interviews were conducted in a semi-structured format (Galletta, 2013, p. 23), with the less structured aspects helping to build up a more intimate understanding of the institutional terrain (Robson and McCartan, 2016, p. 293). We followed the conduct of the ‘semi-standardised’ interview first outlined by Scheele and Groeben (1988), where open questions are followed by more pointed ones. This aimed to realise Hermann’s ‘interview as drama’ (2004) to reveal ‘subjective theories’ in relation to the politics around TPSS. The following seven questions were asked to interviewees - full schema are available on request.

1. I’m interested in how you would describe your present role.
2. What is the external change your organisation is looking to effect?
3. Are there any particular tools your organisation uses, either to measure where you’ve gone, or model where you need to go?
4. What is the knowledge base like across the organisation when it comes to the understanding of this tooling?
5. You mentioned that you engage with (group). Do you have a good working relationship with them?
6. When you want central government to give a project financial support... how do you make that happen?
7. How has your organisation’s evidence building and project planning capability changed over time?

4 Preliminary Results

STBs receive core grants from central government that serve here as an indication of size. **Table 1** and **Figure 1** help clarify this differential. Two STBs - Transport for the North and Midlands Connect - significantly outsize the others and hence are separated off in **Figure 2**.

STB	Local authority count (2024)	Population (000) (2021)	DfT Grant (£000) (2022-23)	DfT Grant per capita
Transport for the North	51	14,829	6,500	43p
Midlands Connect	22	9,443	5,000	52p
Transport for the South East	16	7,227	1,725	23p
England’s Economic Heartland	12	4,845	2,000	41p
Western Gateway	8	2,882	605	21p
Transport East	5	3,311	762	23p
Peninsula Transport	5	2,196	585	27p

Table 1: STB vital statistics (tabular)

Figure 1: STBs vital statistics (visual)

Table 2 lists STBs in order of grant size in relation to their use of TPSS. This illustrates that there is a broad trend at play: the larger an STB is, the more likely it is that they have good organisational knowledge of their own TPSS. However, it is not necessarily the case that a larger STB finds it easier to use these tools instrumentally (in other words, to shape project delivery independently of political priorities). This might be a result of the broader institutional environment, where transport project funding is dictated centrally, and not something an STB controls, regardless of size; the nature of local authority priorities and national competitions for funding can make independent project development by the STBs more difficult. Nonetheless, the preliminary indication from this summary is that data from TPSS does not play an *instrumental* role across several STBs, and hence **cannot directly inform policy outcomes**.

Table 2: Use & Knowledge of TPSS per STB

STB	Standard of organisational knowledge of TPSS	Use of data from TPSS
Transport for the North	Notably good	Usually symbolic role, potential for instrumental role
Midlands Connect	Notably good	Usually symbolic role, potential for instrumental role
England’s Economic Heartland	Notably good	Symbolic role
Transport for the South East	Notably good	Usually symbolic role, potential for instrumental role
Transport East	Satisfactory	Symbolic role
Western Gateway	Could be improved	Usually symbolic role, potential for instrumental role
Peninsula Transport	Could be improved	Symbolic role

Figure 2 shows a further correlation between grant size and breadth of TPSS, as the two larger STBs are overrepresented compared to the other five. Across both groups, the simpler TPSS (dashboards and frameworks) were reported more often. This could be owing to STBs’ relative institutional youth, or cost concerns. The restrictions on grants for STBs means it is harder to operationalise large models, particularly agent-based ones, which, unlike simple frameworks, cannot be re-applied to new spatial contexts without modification. 4-step models remain more common than other models - particularly in the larger STBs, which commit to a greater number of larger projects requiring scrutiny from the DfT and the Treasury.

Figure 2: STBs' self-reported use of different TPSS.

Figure 3 illustrates that staff at STBs most frequently see themselves as providing a strategic direction for central government. While regional priorities are a worthy aim, this result reinforces the suggestion that provisioning local benefit - the core aim of STBs - is less important than national concerns. In terms of barriers to success, we see a vicious circle at play in the regional space: lack of statutory powers (which would further enable instrumental TPSS-based decision-making) are not seen as a key barrier for STBs, in part because they lack the core funding to *actualise* those powers if they attained them. As a result, appending Gudmundsson and Sørensen (2013), we propose **Figure 4** as a framework for taking forward understandings of (T)PSS use, influence and role.

Figure 3: STBs' self-reported opportunities and barriers.

Figure 4: A proposed framework for the cyclical use, influence and role of (T)PSS.

5 Conclusion

Semi-standardised interviews with transport practitioners provide a novel contribution to questions regarding the use, influence and role of large transport-related GIS tools in policy. This applied study suggests that there are serious roadblocks to growth in GIS analytical capability. Effective *use* of TPSS is limited by a lack of funding to build tools, train staff and conduct analysis; in other words, the ultimate *influence* of TPSS is limited at a political level, before technical questions are even under consideration. As such, **Figure 4** outlines in red the line between influence and policy: by recognising the role of TPSS have in determining political outcomes, and deploying them to broaden the scope of GIS tools in that space, practitioners and academics can create the possibility of greater funding for truly data-driven policy-making in future.

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7 Biographies

Claude Lynch is a PhD student at the Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, UCL. The through line of his research is the link between theory and application in geography. Within this, his PhD project aims to understand how simulations from transport models are best applied to regional political contexts.

Gerry Casey is an Associate at Arup and Principal Research Fellow at the Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, UCL. Gerry works on R&D projects in the transportation sector. He is interested in evidence based decision making and modelling for enlightenment, not post-justification.

Esra Suel is an Associate Professor of City Modelling at the Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, UCL. Esra's research focuses on computational methods for analysing built environments and human behaviour in cities. She is motivated by questions in urban mobility, land-use, housing, and social and health inequalities.

Adam Dennett is Professor of Urban Analytics at the Bartlett Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis, UCL. Adam's research interests include migration, mobilities, housing, gentrification, urban modelling and beer geographies; these are tied together with a fondness for data, visualisation and computational methods, put to use in applied settings.

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